

Export Competitiveness of CSEZ and its impact on Labour Standards of Women Workers in the Gem and Jewellery Sector of the Zone

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Jacob, Anupa. "Export Competitiveness of CSEZ and Its Impact on Labour Standards of Women Workers in the Gem and Jewellery Sector of the Zone." *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2019, pp. 12–22.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2586368>

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Abstract

The present study tries to examine how far women workers who form majority in the Gem and Jewellery sector have to bear the brunt of export competitive strategy followed by this sector in Cochin Special Economic Zone (CSEZ). For this, labour standards of the female workforce in the sector are compared with export competitiveness indicators of the sector. Export competitiveness of the sector has been analysed using various competitiveness measures like Industrial Competitiveness Index (ICI) and Revealed Comparative Advantage Index (RCAI) etc. Labour standards of workers are quantified using scaling technique to make it comparable with competitiveness. Gem and Jewellery sector, with very high competitiveness, records the lowest provision of labour standards. Absence of discrimination is rated high for the sector, but absence of trade union participation, wage and social security measures has made this sector's Combined Average Score of labour standards 'moderate'. It shows the extent of exploitation of unorganized female workforce in the Gem and Jewellery sector of the Zone, despite this sector's high level of competitiveness.

Keywords: Labour standards, Competitiveness, Gem and Jewellery sector, Cochin Special Economic Zone(CSEZ), female workers

Introduction

The competitive environment in Special Economic Zones (SEZs) helps to produce quality output at lower cost (Kumar, 2006). To sustain their competitiveness in the export market and to simultaneously maintain a lower cost of production, firms follow the strategy of provision of poor labour standards to its workers. Exceptions are some firms with modern employment practices that provide better standards to enhance the labour productivity.

Labourers working in the Zone face the problem of absence of stringent labour laws. Article 49 of SEZ Act, 2005 specially mentions that all labour laws relating to trade unions, industrial and labour disputes, welfare of labour including conditions of work, etc. are applicable to SEZs. But, with the transfer of powers from Labour Commission to Development commissioner, the labour law

enforcement in Zones is very lax. This makes working condition in the Zones miserable for the workers, especially women workers who are mostly unorganised. This happens when firms in the Zone have a preference to employ female workers as they are hardworking, very diligent and meticulous in their work

This paper attempts to analyse the exact status of working conditions in the Gem and Jewellery sector of Cochin Special Economic Zone (CSEZ), the labour intensive sector which employs unskilled women labourers for its production. The article carries out the analyses of labour standards among women workers in the sector in the context of export competitive policy followed there.

Literature Review

The term competitiveness is different from the term competition. Kathuria (1999) defines competitiveness as the capabilities of a firm or a sector or a nation to compete successfully. As a means of enhancing export competitiveness, Special Economic Zones (SEZs) have been set up in India. Aggarwal (2006) defines Special Economic Zones as industrial clusters where external economies of scale and other advantages help the operating firms in reducing costs, developing competitive production systems and attracting foreign investment

In the export market, SEZs provide an option for corporations to earn large profits out of low wages paid to workers. This is so in countries with large populations of uneducated, poor or educated-unemployed people. India, being a country with large population provides a platform for large corporations to reap the benefits of a competitive wage rate (Sampat, 2008).

Labour standards prescribed by ILO are often violated when the firms have competitiveness-targets to meet. This is especially true in case of Special Economic Zones. Many studies have drawn attention to the intensity of violation of labour laws at SEZs around the world. Elliott and Freeman(2003) argue that often, firms at EPZs are gated colonies to keep the workers in. The managers prevent 'activists' from disclosing information about poor working conditions.

There is an overwhelming presence of females in labour intensive sectors, who are by nature low-skilled. Wage rates and other fringe benefits are provided to them by a lesser amount compared to male workers. Moreover the hours of work are longer than the norms set for industrialised countries. If the wage rates were comparable with developed countries, the very competitive advantage of low labour costs would vanish (Kundra, 2000).

The literature review done thus establishes that there exists a relationship between competitiveness and labour standards.. Often, women workers have to bear the brunt of the competitive strategy in the form of frequent retrenchment, failure to pay minimum wages, sexual harassment, etc. as they are unorganised in any forms of associations like trade unions. In the context of this relationship, several research issues about women workers in SEZs emerge.

Objectives of the Study

- to compare competitiveness and labour standards of women workers in the Gem and Jewellery sector of CSEZ.
- to analyse the present status of labour standards of women workers in the Gem and Jewellery sector of CSEZ.

Methodology and Sampling Technique

The present study focuses on analysis of competitiveness and labour standards in Gem and Jewellery sector of CSEZ, which has large presence of women contract workers. The sector is labour-intensive, contributing to employment, especially women. Gem and Jewellery is composed of 10 operational units and employs about 1030 workers, who are women.

Analysis of Competitiveness

For the analysis of export competitiveness of Gem and Jewellery sector, sector-wise data made available by CSEZ Authority (compiled on the basis of the Annual Progress Report submitted by the SEZ units) is used. Various measures are used to assess competitiveness of the Sector. When Industrial Competitiveness Index (ICI) is used in the study to calculate and compare the competitiveness of sector in the Zone, adapted version of Revealed Comparative Advantage Index (RCAI) is used to analyse the export competitiveness of the sector in CSEZ compared to the exports of the same product/sector from India. These two competitive measures are supported by Total Exports, Percentage Annual Growth Rate of Exports, and Labour productivity (Output-Employment Ratio).

Analysis of Labour Standards

Analysis of labour standards is done through a primary survey of working conditions. A representative size of 30 per cent of the enterprises is selected. Out of 10 enterprises in Gem and Jewellery sector, 3 have been chosen. Second stage involves the selection of workers. Five per cent samples are chosen from the sector. A pretested structured interview schedule is used to elicit reliable, precise and detailed information about the working environment in the Zone

Analysis of Competitiveness and Labour Standards

An attempt is made to quantify labour standards to make it comparable with competitiveness. For this, four important labour standards based on ILO's core conventions are selected. They form: wage, absence of discrimination in wage payment, social security measures and trade union membership. The chosen labour standards existing in Gem and Jewellery sector in the Zone have been reduced to five-point scale, five being the highest and one being the lowest. Average Score for each labour standard and Combined Average Score (CAS) for all the four selected labour standards are then computed. CAS obtained is then rated from 'very high' to 'very low'. By comparing labour standards and competitiveness of each sector, interpretations are drawn.

Results and Discussions

Some of the significant findings that have emerged from the present study about competitiveness and labour standards of women workers in the Gem and Jewellery sector of CSEZ are discussed under the following sub-headings.

Analysis of Competitiveness

Total Exports and Growth of Exports

A time-series analysis of the total exports and growth of exports of Gem and Jewellery sector in the Zone is shown in figures 1 and 2 respectively. For the past many years the sector in the Zone has registered an improved performance in its exports in absolute terms.

Figure 1 Total Exports in Gem and Jewellery Sector

Source: Compiled and Computed from APR of CSEZ (2012)

This highly labour intensive sector is a major source of foreign exchange earnings of the country. Increase in the demand for Indian jewellery abroad and important policy decisions of the government including de-licensing of jewellery imports, as part of economic reforms, has helped in the growth of this sector. The sector has registered a good performance in growth of exports of 23 per cent and 44 per cent in 2007-08 and 2008-09 respectively. Signs of recession are observed only in 2009-10 (Exim bank India, 2010). The same trend is observed in the case of Gem and Jewellery sector in CSEZ too.

Figure 2 Percentage Annual Growth Rate of Exports

Source: Compiled and Computed from APR of CSEZ (2012)

Output-Employment Ratio

Assessing labour productivity is one of the conventional methods of measuring the efficiency of a production unit. Productivity indicates economic growth, competitiveness, efficiency and living standards within an economy. Though there are various measures of calculating labour productivity, the measure used here is output per unit of employment i.e., ratio of output to the number of labourers (OECD, 2008).

$$\text{Output-Employment Ratio} = \text{Volume of output} / \text{Total Employment}$$

Table 1 Output-Employment Ratio

Sector	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12
Gem and Jewellery	236.06	135.09	180.48	2,690.19	8,851.87	14,545.49	15,199.78	20,043.09

Source: Compiled and Computed from APR of CSEZ (2012)

Gem and Jewellery sector has experienced increase in efficiency level. This sector, which is highly labour-intensive, employs unskilled women labourers. Their experience and diligence in their work makes them churn-out the maximum output. Together with this, an increase in the world demand for Indian jewellery makes this sector highly competitive in terms of exports

The Industrial Competitiveness Index (ICI)

It is a composite measure of relative and multidimensional economic performance as measured by profitability, productivity as well as output growth. (Fischer and Schornberg, 2006).

$$\text{COMPS} = f(\text{PROS}, \text{PRODS}, \text{GROS}).$$

The original study mentions the possibility of measuring industry competitiveness using two measures – efficiency measured in terms of productivity and growth of output (Lall, 2001).

$$\text{COMPS} = f(\text{EFFs, GROS}).$$

ICI is constructed based on the methodology used for the calculation of the United Nations’ Human Development Index.

The general formula for calculating individual indices is,

$$\text{Indices, I} = \frac{\text{Actual Value} - \text{Minimum Value}}{\text{Maximum Value} - \text{Minimum Value}}$$

ICI is then calculated as the simple average of the individual indices.

Table 2 ICI of Gem and Jewellery sector

Sector	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12
Gem and Jewellery	0.32	0.56	0.31	0.38	0.38	0.52

Source: Compiled and Computed from APR of CSEZ (2012)

ICI scores of the Gem and Jewellery sector is found to be increasing over the years, though at a low rate.

Revealed Comparative Advantage Index (RCAI)

Revealed Comparative Advantage Index (RCAI) is used in the present analysis to compare the export competitiveness of Gem and Jewellery sector with respect to the total Gem and Jewellery exports of the country.

Revealed comparative advantage (RCAI), an Index devised by Balassa (1965) is commonly used to measure export competitiveness to identify the sectors in which an economy has a comparative advantage, by comparing the country of interests’ trade profile with the world average (Nag, 2009). If the Index exceeds unity (RCAI > 1), the country is said to have a revealed comparative advantage in the product and vice versa.

In the present study, the measure has been modified to compare CSEZ exports with the India’s exports. The measure is adapted in to the form,

$$\text{RCAI} = \frac{\text{CSEZ Export of Product X}}{\text{CSEZ's Total Export}} \bigg/ \frac{\text{India Export of the Product X}}{\text{India's Total Export}}$$

The result obtained for the sector is summarised in table 3.

Table 3 RCAI of Sectors in CSEZ

Sector	2004-05	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12
Gem and Jewellery	0.42	0.31	2.32	8.71	7.89	7.83	7.53	7.60

Source: Computed from the data collected from Ministry of Commerce available in www.commerce.nic.in, www.deity.gov.in referred on May , 2013

The RCA Index calculated for the sectors confirm that sector has high competitive advantage. RCA for this highly labour intensive sector in 2011-12 is 7.60, above unity. Gem and Jewellery is a major export item for India. Fifteen per cent of India’s merchandise exports is composed of Gem and Jewellery (Economic Survey 2011-12). The prominence of this sector in exports is visible in the Zone too.

Consolidated Scores for Competitiveness

Sector-wise consolidated data on export competitiveness of Gem and Jewellery sector in the Zone for the year 2011-12 is presented in table 4.

Table 4 Competitiveness (2011-12)

Indicators	Gem and Jewellery
Percentage Annual Growth Rate of Exports	53.5
Output-Employment Ratio	20,043.09*
Industrial Competitiveness Index	0.52
Revealed Comparative Advantage Index	7.60

Source: Computed from secondary data

Figures in bracket show ranks

*Higher value of Gem and Jewellery's Output-Employment Ratio indicates high value of gold

All the indicators confirm very high competitiveness of this sector. In terms of RCAI, Gem and Jewellery sector is competitive as its index is greater than unity.

Labour Standards

An attempt has been made to quantify the labour standards of Gem and Jewellery sector using scaling technique to make it comparable with competitiveness.. This is done through the analysis of the responses of the employees on various aspects of labour standards. Worker's response towards satisfaction derived from four most important labour aspects - Wage, Absence of Discrimination, Social Security Measures and Trade Union Membership is considered. The chosen labour standards existing in each sector in the Zone have been reduced to five-point scale, five being the highest and one being the lowest.

Wage

Wages are a determinant factor in workers' well-being. Considering its important role, workers are asked to indicate their satisfaction levels with regard to the monthly wages they draw. The results are reported in table 5.

Table 5 Percentage Distribution of Workers by Agreement on Satisfactory Wages Drawn

Sector	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not At All
Gem and Jewellery	22.6	64.5	12.9	-	-

Source: Primary Survey

Gem and Jewellery sector is the sector has a low dissatisfaction level (12.9%). To the irony, more than 80 per cent of the workers earn less than Rs 10,000. Considering their (poor) education and skill (acquired) level they accept the existing wage.

Satisfaction level with respect to working conditions is rated. For this, wage is singled-out as evaluation criteria. The wages in the Zone have been rated on a five-point scale by collecting responses to whether they receive 'very high wage', 'high wage', 'moderate wage', 'low wage', and 'very low wage'. Coincidentally, it has been noticed that most of the workers with a wage more than Rs 20000, 15000-20000, 10000-15000, 5000-10000, and less than 5000 were in the above

respective categories. They are given scores in descending order starting from five to one. Number of respondents under each category is taken as the weight and is multiplied with the respective scale. Score obtained for wages is presented in table 6.

Table 6 Labour Standards (Wage) Score

Sector	Scale					Total Score	Average Score
	1	2	3	4	5		
Gem and Jewellery	2	23	3	1	2	71	2.29

Source: Computed from primary data

Total Score: Sum of (no. of respondents * scale)

Average Score: Total Score / No. of responses

Absence of Discrimination

Gender discrimination in wage is another factor considered. Workers in Gem and Jewellery are largely female workers. So the discrimination is reported only by less than five per cent..

Table 7 Percentage Distribution of Workers by Agreement on Absence of Gender-discrimination in Wages Paid

Sector	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Not At All
Gem and Jewellery	32.3	64.5	3.2	-	-

Source: Primary Survey

Absence of discrimination is rated and is directly represented on the five-point scale. The respondents' agreement of absence of discrimination is categorised as 'Strongly Agree', 'Agree', 'Disagree', 'Strongly Disagree', and 'Not at All', which are respectively given 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 scale. The average score obtained for the sector is shown in table 8.

Table 8 Labour Standards (Absence of Discrimination) Score

Sector	Scale					Total Score	Average Score
	1	2	3	4	5		
Gem and Jewellery	0	0	1	20	10	133	4.29

Source: Computed from primary data

Total Score: Sum of (no. of respondents * scale)

Average Score: Total Score / No. of responses

It is understood that as only a few workers have registered their dissatisfaction with respect to absence of gender equality in wage payment, the average score for all the sectors is nearly four or greater than four in all the sectors.

Social Security Measures

Social security measures are the facilities like provident fund, gratuity, bonus, and insurance like ESI. When all these four facilities are offered to the workers, they were given five points. Those with three schemes, two schemes, one scheme and no scheme are respectively given 4, 3, 2 and 1 point. The number of respondents receiving the corresponding package of social security measures is given respective scales.

Table 9 Labour Standards (Social Security Measures) Score

Sector	Scale					Total Score	Average Score
	1	2	3	4	5		
Gem and Jewellery	0	23	5	0	3	76	2.45

Source: Computed from primary data

Total Score: Sum of (no. of respondents * scale)

Average Score: Total Score / No. of responses

The women workers in this sector are provided with the least social security measures as is understood from table 9.

Trade Union Membership

The percentage of women workers with trade union membership is also rated on five-point scale. The respective choice variables are, no trade union, limited trade union involvement (i.e. less than 25 per cent workers are union members), moderate trade union involvement (i.e. 25-50 per cent of workers are union members), high trade union involvement (i.e. 50-75 per cent of workers are union members), and very high trade union involvement (i.e. more than 75 per cent of workers are union members). They were given 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 scores respectively.

Table 10 Labour Standards (Trade Union Membership) Score

Sector	Scale					Total Score	Average Score
	1	2	3	4	5		
Gem and Jewellery	Nil	-	-	-	-	-	1

Source: Computed from primary data

Average Score: Total Score / No. of responses

With a 'public utility status' conferred up on SEZ, the freedom to form trade unions and declare strikes remains curtailed. CSEZ has the presence of CITU, which is the prominent trade union present there. INTUC and BJP's wing have diminutive presence in the Zone. However, trade union activity is completely absent in Gem and Jewellery sector.

Consolidated Scores for Labour Standards

Combined Average Score of labour standards is estimated. This will provide a quantitative approximation of the labour standards provided in each sector, which is necessary for its comparison with competitiveness indicators.

The Combined Average Score (CAS) for the sector is given in table 11. It is the simple average of the four averages score of labour standards calculated for the sector. CAS Scores are such that, CAS of 0-1.4 is rated as 'Very Low' sector, with CAS of 1.5 to 2.4 as 'Low', with CAS of 2.5 to 3.4 as 'Moderate', with CAS of 3.5 to 4.4 as 'High', and with CAS score of above 4.5 gets the rating 'Very High'.

Table 11 Scores of Labour Standards

Labour Standards	Gem and Jewellery
Wage	2.29
Absence of Discrimination	4.29
Social Security Measures	2.45
Trade Union Participation	1
Combined Average Score (CAS)	2.50
Rating of CAS	Moderate

Source: Computed from primary data

The Combined Average Score (CAS) of labour standards found out for the sectors reveals that Gem and Jewellery sector has moderately rated working conditions. In the light of various indicators that reveal the competitiveness position of the sector, it is to be analysed further how far the labour standards, in terms of CAS, are sacrificed or upheld for gaining export competitiveness in the Gem and Jewellery sector.

Labour Standards and Competitiveness

It is already understood, that Gem and Jewellery sector in the Zone has improved its competitiveness position over the years. The four important labour standards among women workers in the Gem and Jewellery sector the Zone, quantified on the basis of CAS are analysed and compared with the competitiveness of the sectors. This will throw some light on the relationship which exists between them in CSEZ.

Gem and Jewellery sector in the Zone has been registering a noteworthy level of competitiveness. The RCA Index calculated for the sector shows that the sector has competitive advantage. It also shows the contribution made by the Gem and Jewellery sector of the Zone to all-India exports. The sector is having high percentage annual growth of exports. The sector shows very high labour productivity in terms of output-employment ratio. Thus all the measures, except ICI confirm very high competitiveness for the Gem and Jewellery sector.

Table 12 Competitiveness and Labour Standards (Gem and Jewellery)

(a)

Competitiveness Indicators	Results
Percentage Annual Growth Rate of Exports	53.5 (1)
Output-Employment Ratio	20,043.09
Industrial Competitiveness Index	0.52 (6)
Revealed Comparative Advantage Index	7.60

Source: Computed from primary data

(b)

Labour Standards	Rating
Wage	Low
Absence of Discrimination	High
Social Security Measures	Moderate
Trade Union Participation	Very Low (Nil)
Combined Average Score	Moderate

Figures in bracket show ranks

As against the ‘high’ competitiveness, the CAS is the lowest (2.5) in the Gem and Jewellery sector at ‘moderate’ level. Wages are ‘low’ in this sector which is largely composed of women unorganised workers. Social security measures for the workers who do meticulous work is reported to be at ‘moderate’ level. It is low with score of 2.45. Trade union participation in this sector is also reported to be nil, which only proves that women workers have low inclination towards

joining trade unions. It also stresses their weak bargaining power. Absence of discrimination on the basis of gender gets 'high' rating, as it is to be noted that females form higher proportion of total workforce and male workers are almost nil.

As the competitiveness maintained in the sector is very high and the labour standards get a very low score, it can be understood that the labour standards are compromised in the sector. When the high competitiveness enjoyed by the sector is compared with respect to the poor labour standards enjoyed by the sector, the notion that labour standards are poor in the sector gets proved. Thus the worst labour standards are recorded for women workers in Gem and Jewellery, the sector with the best competitiveness position.

Conclusion

Keeping in view the competitive position that Gem and Jewellery sector is in, due care should also be given to the welfare implications of promoting SEZs. The purpose of establishment of SEZs will be defeated if attention is not paid to the well-being of these female labourers. Their productivity will get compromised in the long run if they are not fairly rewarded. A balanced strategy of preserving the interests of both the investors and labourers should be adopted, if the export competitiveness is to be preserved for the long run. As a result, SEZs can play an effective role in ensuring competitiveness and simultaneously aid in human capital formation and poverty alleviation.

Scope for Further Study

The present study has explored the realities about the competitiveness and labour standards in the Gem and Jewellery sector, the sector with the most number of women in the Zone. The findings of the study can prove to be useful for policy makers and the government to frame appropriate strategies aimed at promoting the interests of not only the firms but also the women working class in the Zone.

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